

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ECO-ACCOUNTING SYSTEMS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN BAYELSA STATE

BY

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Abstract

The study examined assessment of the impact of eco-accounting systems on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational design. The population consisted 341 registered small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. A sample of 324 Proprietors were used for analysis. The instrument was a self-developed questionnaire titled assessment of the impact of eco-accounting systems on the Performance of Small and Medium scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State. The instrument was rated on four-point scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation unit in the Department of Counselling and Educational Psychology in the Faculty of Education, Niger Delta University. Cronbach alpha determined reliability of the instrument to obtain reliability coefficient value of 0.95. Data was analyzed with Statistical Packages for Social Sciences. The results revealed significant relationship between eco-accounting systems and social costs, and contingency costs on the performance of small and medium scale small scale enterprises. The study concluded that costs impact small and medium scale enterprises' performance. The study recommended amongst others costs minimization to improve profit performance of enterprises.

Keywords: *Assessment, Impact, Eco-accounting Systems, Performance, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises*

Introduction

Eco-accounting systems is a combining form of representing environmental and green accounting systems which is a method of measuring in economic terms the performance of any type of organization in relation to the environment. The eco-accounting systems is the proper careful costing and assessment of intended usage of enterprises' resources, their benefits, liabilities and utilizing them positively to improve the performance of businesses economically and the physical business environment. The eco-accounting system is the identification of resources usage, measurement and communication of environmental costs, environmental liabilities, environmental benefits, effects of the natural environment on a company in monetary terms and measurement of the influence a company

has on the environment in physical terms (Frank, 2003, Lei, et al, 2014 & Igbodo et al, 2017).

Performance refers to superior results achieved by small and medium scale enterprises at a specific moment in time compared to the previous period (Antonio et al, 2011). Organizational performance is the ability of an organization to utilize its resources efficiently and generate outputs that are consistent with its goals and objectives and relevant for its clients and stakeholders (Charity, 2011). Organizational performance is best described with the ability of management to develop and use available human resources, knowledge and competences in achieving profit maximization and optimization.

Small and medium scale enterprises on the other hand, are the basis for many nations' economic growth and development all over the world. The concept of small and medium scale enterprises has no universally accepted definition. Its definition varies from country to country, agency to agency, body to body, and even within sectors in countries based on employees, revenues or fixed assets. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (2017) defined small and medium on the following criteria: Small scale enterprises are business with ten to forty-nine people with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million naira, while a medium scale enterprise has fifty to one hundred and ninety-nine employees with a year turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million naira.

European Union Commission (2005) defined small enterprises as businesses with employment of fifty (50) people and asset and capital turnover of seven (7) to ten (10) million Naira only. While medium enterprises are businesses with employment of two hundred and fifty (250) persons with asset and capital turnover of forty (40) to fifty (50) million Naira only.

Statement of the Problem

Small and medium scale enterprises are the basis for economic growth of nations all over the World. They contribute to employment creation, growth in gross domestic product, growth in export earnings and internally generated revenue. Small and medium scale enterprises are life-wire and wheel of progress of economic growth of Bayelsa State. In spite of these significant contributions to economic growth and development of Bayelsa State, impact of small and medium scale enterprises recently are faced with decrease in quantity of sales volume, profit, and low patronage which has led to closure of many enterprises. These entities include fast foods enterprises, boutiques, bakery production enterprises,

transportation enterprises, supermarkets, information communication technology outfits, etc.

Perhaps this is as a result of lack of good costs accounting systems impact assessment of proprietors of enterprises. If this ugly trend is not averted economic growth of enterprises in Bayelsa State will no longer be experience soonest. It is against this background that the study assess the impact of eco-accounting systems on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State in terms of social costs and contingency costs.

1.3 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. How does social costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?
2. How does contingency costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. Social costs does not significantly impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.
2. Contingency costs does not significantly impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of the study was to assess the impact of eco-accounting systems on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Specifically, the study assesses whether:

1. The impact of social costs on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

2. The impact of contingency costs on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Eco-accounting system is the identification of resources usage, measurement and communication of environmental costs, economic costs, social costs, contingency costs, environmental liabilities, environmental benefits, effects of the natural environment on a company in monetary terms and measurement of the influence a company has on the environment in physical terms (Lei et al, 2014, & Igbodo et al, 2017). The eco-accounting systems is the proper careful costing and assessment of intended usage of enterprises' resources, their benefits, liabilities and utilizing them positively to improve the performance of businesses economically and the physical business environment.

Social costs and performance of small and medium scale enterprises

Social costs are all costs incurred for production of commodities by firms which causes some damages or losses to others which firms does not take into account while taking decisions regarding price and output of commodities (Agilemania, 2025). The external damages or benefits, if any, caused by the production of products of a firm to customers or to her firms or people around the environment constitutes parts of social costs which sometimes ignored by enterprises. For instance, the harmful effects caused for production of pesticide (negative odour, smell), emission or polluted air, economic damages, emitting smokes and toxic wastes of factories poured into rivers, streams and lakes create health hazard for people living in the surroundings but firms do not make any payment to others who bear the external costs of production firms. The beneficial external effects created by production activities of firms

are called positive externalities, while the negative effects are called negative externalities. The social costs are the sum total of the private costs and the net of negative externalities over positive externalities.

According to Mirela (2012) Costs of social activities are (costs for the protection of nature, reforestation, improving the ecological landscapes, supporting several local activities, organizing seminars and other social activities), and costs representing damages (costs for soil remediation, sanctions, penalties, litigations etc). Social costs and benefits refer to the total costs and benefits to society from a particular activity or policy, including both private and external impacts.

Social costs is the total costs to society from a specific activity, encompassing both private costs (incurred directly by the individual or firm) and external costs (impacts on third parties not involved in the activity). Examples of these costs are: Private Costs; Wages, raw materials, rent, etc. External Costs; Pollution, traffic congestion, noise, etc.

Contingency costs and performance of small and medium scale enterprises

Contingency costs is an estimated costs amount set aside by the enterprises owners or managers in order to account for any unknown risks and unexpected losses associated with businesses. Contingency costs refers to costs that probably occur based on past experiences but with some uncertainty regarding the amount of money. Contingency costs are made or provided to carter for unforeseen events, risks, disaster expenses act in the costs estimation accounting system in an enterprise to improve the performance of small medium enterprises. Contingency costs acts as an insurance policies or reserves funding sources that allow work to be completed on schedule time without cutting costs in other areas or increasing the budget. Contingency costs are predetermined specific capital kept aside for

covering risks, unforeseen expenses, or modifications that might badly impact the budget of the entity. Contingency costs include a design error that may occur leading to an unexpected increase in material expenses before ground-breaking, bad weather that may bring rain to overflow a project site to delay work, natural disaster, fire out breaks, global pandemic, terrorist attacks etc that a business, government, individuals etc make to reduce damages done by unforeseen negative events. Health emergency, auto maintenance and repairs, insurance losses, high inflation rate, exchange rate and other financial emergencies are all examples of contingency costs.

The concept of Small Medium Scale Enterprises

The concept of small and medium scale enterprises has no universally accepted definition. Its definition varies from country to country, agency to agency, body to body, and even within sectors in countries based on employees, revenues or fixed assets. Small and Medium Enterprises Development Agency of Nigeria (2017) defined small and medium on the following criteria: Small scale enterprises are business with ten to forty-nine people with an annual turnover of five to forty-nine million naira, while a medium scale enterprise has fifty to one hundred and ninety-nine employees with a year turnover of fifty to four hundred and ninety-nine million naira.

Research Method

The study adopted correlational survey design which is a form of research design that finds out the extent of relationship between two or more variables, and data from such variables that are in ratio or interval scale scores to create the possibility for the scores to be correlated (Nwankwo, 2016).

The targeted population consisted of three hundred and forty one registered small and medium scale enterprises operating in Bayelsa State (Bayelsa State Ministry of Trade,

Industry and Investment, 2024). Proprietors of the whole three hundred and forty-one (341) registered small and medium scale enterprises were used as respondents.

A census sample size of the study consisted of the whole three hundred and forty one (341) proprietors of registered small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. Since the census sample size was manageable there was no sampling technique used.

The instrument for data collection was a self-developed questionnaire titled “Assessment of the Impact of Eco-accounting Systems on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Questionnaire (AIESPSMSEQ) in Bayelsa State”. Each of the items was measured on four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA)-4 point, Agree (A)-3 point, Disagree (D)-2 point and Strongly Disagree (SD)-1 point. The instrument contains fifteen (15) questionnaire items that sought for useful information on Assessment of the Impact of Eco-accounting Systems on the Performance of Small and Medium scale Enterprises in Bayelsa State. The items were distributed as follows: 1-5, 6-10, 11-15 for eco-accounting system, social costs, and contingency costs.

The instrument was validated by two experts from Measurement and Evaluation Unit of the Department of Counselling and Educational Psychology in the Faculty of Education in Niger Delta University. The comments, observations, corrections and suggestions of the two experts during the process of validation of the instrument were used to draft and modify the final copy of the questionnaire to enhance the validity of the instrument.

Reliability of the instrument Assessment of the Impact of Eco-accounting Systems on the Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Questionnaire (AIESPSMSEQ) in Bayelsa State was administered to 50 proprietors of small and medium scale

enterprises in Rivers State who were not part of the original population of the study.

The instrument was administered once to 50 respondents and the scores obtained were subjected to Cronbach alpha analysis to establish the internal consistency of the instrument variables. The reliability coefficient values for the variables were as follows: social costs 0.920, contingency costs 0.980, and the entire instrument 0.95 respectively.

The administration of the instrument was carried out personally by the researcher with the support of two assistants. A total of 341 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents. Total of 324 Questionnaire

were retrieved for the analysis representing 95% successful retrieval. While 17 copies were not retrieved for the analysis representing 5% unsuccessful retrieval. The questionnaire was retrieved after one day interval.

The data collected was analyzed Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS)'s Simple Linear Regression statistical tool was used to analyze the research questions and test the corresponding hypotheses.

Results

Research Question One

How does social costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Table 1: Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.999 ^a	.998	.997	5.465

a. Predictors: (Constant), ECO-ACCOUNTING

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	30321.020	1	30321.020	1015.272	.001 ^b
	Residual	59.730	2	29.865		
	Total	30380.750	3			

a. Dependent Variable: SOCIAL COST

b. Predictors: (Constant), ECO-ACCOUNTING

		Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	
		Coefficients		Coefficients			
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-11.862	4.001		-2.965	.097	
	ECO-ACCOUNTING	1.150	.036	.999	31.863	.001	

a. Dependent Variable: SOCIAL COST

Table 4.7, shows Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The table reveals that 324 respondents’ responses were analyzed. A correlation coefficient (r) of .999 was obtained, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive strong relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase social cost of small and medium scale enterprises. The r^2 is .998, therefore the variation in social cost of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is .998 x100 which is 99.8%. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 99.8%.

Research Question Two

How does contingency costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State?

Table 2: Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1	.998 ^a	.997	.995	6.37953	

a. Predictors: (Constant), ECO-ACCOUNTING

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	23600.603	1	23600.603	579.890	.002 ^b

Residual	81.397	2	40.698
Total	23682.000	3	

a. Dependent Variable: CONTINGENCY COST

b. Predictors: (Constant), ECO-ACCOUNTING

Coefficients ^a							
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	-1.147	4.670			-.246	.829
	ECO-ACCOUNTING	1.014	.042	.998		24.081	.002

a. Dependent Variable: CONTINGENCY COST

Table 2, shows Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The table reveals that 324 respondents’ responses were analyzed. A correlation coefficient (r) of .998 was obtained, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive strong relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises. The r² is .997, therefore the variation contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is .997 x100 which is 99.7%. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 99.7%.

Research Hypothesis One

There is not significant relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Table 3 Test of Significance of Simple Linear Regression Analysis Correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises

Variable	N	Df	R	p-value or sig	Alpha level	Decision
Eco-accounting and Social cost	324	322	.999	.001	0.05	Sig p<0.05

Table 3, reveals the test of significance of simple linear regression correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. It can be deduced from the table an observed probability value (p-value) or sig of .001 at 0.05 level of significance with 322 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, r at 322 = .999, p<0.05). Since the p-value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis

of “There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is rejected. Hence the alternative hypothesis is upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Research Hypothesis Two

There is not significant relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost

Table 4 Test of Significance of Simple Linear Regression Analysis Correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting system and environment cost among small and medium scale enterprises

Variable	N	Df	R
Eco-accounting and Contingency cost	324	322	.998

Table 4, reveals the test of significance of simple linear regression correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and contingency cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. It can be deduced from the table an observed probability value (p-value) or sig of .002 at 0.05 level of significance with 322 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, r at $322 = .998$, $p < 0.05$). Since the p-value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis of “There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting and contingency cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is rejected. Hence the alternative hypothesis is upheld. Thus, there is a significant relationship between eco-accounting and contingency cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State

Discussion

The findings of the study showed that there is a significant relationships eco-accounting systems and social cost, and contingency cost on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Research Question One investigated how does social costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State? The data analysis results reveal Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between

on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

eco-accounting system and social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The Table reveals that 324 respondents’ responses were analyzed. A correlation coefficient (r) of .999 was obtained, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive strong relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase social cost of small and medium

scale enterprises. The r^2 is .998, therefore the variation in social cost of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is .998 x100 which is 99.8%. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the social cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 99.8%. This finding corroborated the findings of European Union Commission (2003) that environmental management accounting system focuses on making internal business strategy decisions. It can be defined as: the identification, collection, analysis and use of two types of information for internal decision making, physical information on the use, flows and fates of energy, water and materials including waste, monetary information on environmentally related costs, earnings, and savings etc.

The result from Hypothesis One test of significance of simple linear regression correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State was significant at probability value (p-value) or sig of .001 at 0.05 level of significance with 322 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, r at $322 = .999$, $p < 0.05$). Since the p-value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis of “There is no significant relationship between eco-

accounting and social cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is rejected. Hence the alternative hypothesis is upheld.

Research Question Two investigated how does contingency costs impact the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State? The data analysis results reveal Model Summary of Simple Linear Regression correlation analysis of the relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The table reveals that 324 respondents' responses were analyzed. A correlation coefficient (r) of .998 was obtained, implying a positive strong relationship between eco-accounting system and contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State. The positive strong relationship implies that an increase in eco-accounting system will result to an increase contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises. The r^2 is .997, therefore the variation in contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises that can be accounted for by eco-accounting system in Bayelsa state is $.997 \times 100$ which is 99.7%. This means the influence of eco-accounting system on the contingency cost of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is 99.7%. The findings corroborate the findings of European Union Commission (2003) that contingency costs is used to provide information needed by external stakeholders on a company's financial performance. This type of accounting allows companies to prepare financial reports for investors, lenders and other interested parties. The result from Hypothesis Two test of significance of simple linear regression correlation of the relationship between eco-accounting and contingency cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State was significant at probability value (p -value) or sig of .002 at 0.05 level of significance with 322 degrees of freedom, which is less than the chosen alpha level, r at

$322 = .998, p < 0.05$). Since the p -value is less than the chosen alpha level, the null hypothesis of "There is no significant relationship between eco-accounting and contingency cost among small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State is rejected. Hence the alternative hypothesis is upheld.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the study concluded that social costs and contingency costs negatively impact performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Bayelsa State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the study recommended the following:

1. Proprietors of small and medium scale enterprises should minimize costs to improve performance of enterprises in Bayelsa State.
2. Government of Bayelsa State should unify taxation policies to reduce the excessive multiple taxes paid to strengthen financial growth of enterprises.

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